

Project Architecture

Deliverable n. 1: Report on availability and status of the testbed

CERN – Be-ys

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Project Description

With the COVID-19 pandemic, our globalised world has engaged in faster digitalisation. Healthcare is becoming one of the main driving sectors for digitalised services. Large and complex epidemics, and more generally speaking diseases with high societal and economic impact, such as neurodegenerative conditions like Alzheimer's, Parkinson's or SLA pathologies require innovative research methodologies based on significant personal sensitive data transfer and access. Very similar needs where multiple stakeholders are involved in the data lifecycle have arisen in industrial applications, control systems, and a growing number of applications use data collected "at the edge" and analyse it across distributed computing and data networks, for example for autonomous vehicles fleet operations. All these scenarios have in common the compelling need to collect and store large amounts of data, to move it across a mix of public and private infrastructures, and to analyse it on heterogeneous computing platforms using different types of workloads, from simple data mining to more sophisticated applications of Machine Learning and Deep Learning. As the distribution and processing of data become more widely used, so are the risks of compromising confidential or protected information to the point of becoming a potential showstopper to large-scale operations.

Different approaches to privacy and confidentiality preservation are being explored today, especially considering new regulations such as GDPR and equivalent regulations in the world. An emerging concept in the field is that of Private or Confidential Computing, whereby data is protected (e.g. by means of encryption or anonymisation) across all stages of the data lifecycle. Several commercial cloud providers like Google or Microsoft have for instance recently proposed pilots using encrypted VMs. The future of large-scale data analysis systems, especially in areas where sensitive data is processed, requires new, secure ways of protecting the data.

Typically, a Confidential Computing platform protects four areas of activity:

- 1) **Data at rest:** protecting data stored in repositories, typically using suitable encryption systems.
- 2) **Data in transit:** protecting data as it is transferred across the network, typically by encrypting the contents, the channel, or both.
1. **Data Processing:** protecting data and models as they are analysed/trained/inferred, using techniques such as Secure Multi Party Computation protocols (SMPC) or ML/DL-compatible encryption schemes (e.g. homomorphic encryption and partial functional encryption).
2. **Operations:** recording and auditing transactions, managing AuthN/AuthZ, provenance, etc., typically using technologies like blockchain ledgers, x509 security frameworks, etc.

The QUANTUMACY project ambition is to support the move towards confidential computing and informational self-determination by integrating the relevant technologies into core QKD-enabled services requiring key issuance and distribution, and thus lead a new approach to making data available and processed under the so-called principle of polymorphic privacy.

To do so, QUANTUMACY will create a small-scale, proof-of-concept platform, where existing encryption techniques are combined and extended to use the openQKD infrastructure across the different layers of the platform and test on concrete healthcare use-cases can be performed.

Objectives

CERN and Be-ys, in collaboration with technology providers such as Intel, academic institutes, and healthcare and medical research organisations, have started a year ago the **Living Lab project**, which aims at investigating GDPR-compliant healthcare data systems, by implementing technologies for secure data collection and storage (big data), access (blockchain) and analysis (AI). Joint research on privacy-preserving data analysis techniques is currently being performed in collaboration with the Universidad de Carlos III Madrid – as part of the CERN Doctoral Programme. More recently collaborations with international medical research centres like the Seoul National University of Bundang Hospital (SNUBH) have been set up to include relevant medical expertise.

As part of the ongoing activities aiming to go beyond the state-of-the-art in addressing privacy-by-design (thanks to PET¹ and TET² technologies), the QUANTUMACY consortium focuses on the specific aspects of QKD integration. The QUANTUMACY project therefore builds on the current investigations to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) Define a blueprint privacy-by-design/default architecture for end-to-end QKD-based secure data analysis including data storage, transfer, analysis, and auditing.
- 2) Experiment with polymorphic privacy for data accesses and processing to implement informational self-determination principles thus addressing the GDPR founding principles.
- 3) For each of the functional areas, select a best-in-class encryption technology and adapt it as necessary to make use of QKD.
- 4) Deploy a first testbed based on simulated QKD to address the necessary integration aspects without unduly stressing the nascent openQKD infrastructure.
- 5) In collaboration with the openQKD resources managers, deploy a final testbed version to validate the concepts on real QKD resources and to demonstrate feasibility.
- 6) Realistic medical research use-case will be implemented for validation. More specifically, (i) early detection of neurological disease using a Deep Learning-based MRI images analysis; and (ii) regression analysis of aggregated data from multiple distributed sources. In this initial proof-of-concept, anonymised datasets will be sourced from publicly available or accessible providers, such as University of Stanford's image bank, or the ADNI initiative (<http://adni.loni.usc.edu/>) based on specific agreements.

¹ Positron emission tomography (PET) is a functional imaging technique that uses radioactive substances known as radiotracers to visualize and measure changes in metabolic processes, and in other physiological activities including blood flow, regional chemical composition, and absorption.

² Transmission and Emission Tomography (TET) technology combines acquisition of SPECT (Single-Photon Emission Computed Tomography) and CT (Computed Tomography) data using the same imaging device, thus allowing perfect overlay of anatomic and functional images (Read More: <https://www.ajronline.org/doi/full/10.2214/ajr.183.3.1830655>)

It is to be noted that the computing and analysis technologies will not be developed as part of this project, as they are either already available or will further be developed outside QUANTUMACY, thanks to ongoing activities and projects. **QUANTUMACY will focus on integration with QKD technologies** and on assessing challenges and potential benefits.

The QUANTUMACY project will go beyond the state-of-the-art. PET and TET technologies today allow to protect isolated data and to share over acceptable conditions of security and privacy, but most platforms can barely cope with the richness and volumes of data and none has succeeded yet to conform with all of the founding principles of GDPR and in particular with informational self-determination.

Much awaited next generation transactional data sharing and processing platforms (i.e., based on marketplaces) in Europe's Digital Single Market (DSM) will however have to address the entire data lifecycle and associated regulations, so to guarantee end-to-end security and privacy. Not only will this make such platforms legally sound, but it will give stronger foundations to people's trust in digital services, thus unlocking data and new usages. Beyond the regulatory impact, the proposed investigations on novel ways of implementing secure, privacy-preserving, large-scale data analysis infrastructures would also make an impact on scientific and industrial applications where data and models confidentiality is currently a limiting factor. While actively working on the integration of QKD technologies, even if initially at small-scale, the proposed instantiation of a concrete use-case based on real-world medical research will provide greater insights on further scalability and feasibility.

The results will be made open to additional participants and use-cases (on their own and matching funds) as identified during the project and will allow to raise further awareness on the technology and its potential, while contributing to shared experiences across the openQKD community.

The proposed architecture in QUANTUMACY integrates three major technological blocks addressing the main principles underlying the European GDPR. The three selected blocks have already been tested in ongoing EU projects, such as H2020 MyHealthMyData and H2020 CUREX, and are being extended in CERN openlab's Living Lab project and in the development of a new Be-ys product so-called "ProRegister" and its pending patent (entitled "General Data Protection Method (GDPM)" - EP 17 305 622.7). The developments carried out in MyHealthMyData and more particularly the ProRegister product have recently been awarded by the EC and are being promoted in the European Commission's DSM Innovation Radar as "high growth" and "market impact" potential (<https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/36750>).

The project will achieve the following specific objectives:

1. QKD blockchain for end-to-end traceability (privacy-by-design) – Be-ys

QUANTUMACY will further extend the Living Lab anonymisation process and blockchain to secure key issuance and distribution for its consensus algorithm (transaction signatures) and user IDs, making a step further into privacy-by-design. While these concepts were initially pioneered by MyHealthMyData and recently disclosed as the first GDPR compliant blockchain in Europe, QUANTUMACY will move towards a QKD-enabled version of the platform thus making it the first of its kind.

2. QKD-based encryption for polymorphic privacy (informational self-determination) – Be-ys

QUANTUMACY will pioneer the so-called General Data Protection Method (patent EP 17 305 622.7) and thus implement the first data access protocol encoding processing purpose, consent and conservation time into the data thus making it impossible to hack, conserve or misuse data for unwanted processing purposes. This will be the first QKD-based version and instance of the GDPM patent in Europe, materialising informational self-determination.

3. QKD-based secure data analysis for distributed processing (privacy-by-default) – CERN, Madrid & SNUBH

QUANTUMACY will complement the blockchain GDPR registry and data access protocol with a QKD-enabled secure protocol for distributed data processing to make it possible to process encrypted datasets, from which plain aggregate data or encrypted results can be extracted and shared. While the problem of analysing encrypted data is not a trivial one and its is addressed in other projects, QUANTUMACY intends to make strides into demonstrating the feasibility of a secure end-to-end architecture and make impact in the concrete translation of GDPR (and data protection laws in general) into future fully secure and private transactional data exchange and processing platforms.

Project Phases and Planning

The work plan is organized in three main phases:

Set up (PM1-PM2)

Testbed setup: this phase consists in the creation of the testbed elements across the consortium partners, the data and image repository and the benchmark analysis pipeline. The selected use case consists in early detection of Alzheimer's cases using CNN-based analysis of MRI brain scans. CNNs represent the state of the art as far as extraction of complex features from high resolution images is concerned, studying their performance in conjunction with privacy preserving techniques (and HE in particular) for realistic use cases will have a major impact in different fields. The CNN model is developed in collaboration with experts from SNUBH.

Deliverables/Milestones: Report on availability and status of the testbed (this document)

Integration (PM3-PM9):

Implementation of workflow based on "classic" protocols, integration with simulated QKD. The workflows will support the selected use cases and will allow the extraction and pre-processing of the encrypted images, training of CNN models, SMPC and/or HE-based inference, data fusion across distributed datasets, training and inference of regression models, etc. Different methods will be considered, as for example, homomorphic encryption with Intel nGraph-HE and CKKS encryption, or Secure Multi-Party Computation protocols across the testbed computing sites. Transactions will be recorded using a blockchain based protocol, operations of assignment and removal of user consent will also be tested. Once the base pipelines are in place, the areas where integration with QKD is possible and desirable will be adapted using simulated QKD like the qkdsim toolkit or other suitable technology.

Deliverables/Milestones: Report on availability and status of the testbed; publication of pipeline and preliminary analysis results

Validation (PM7-PM12):

Integration with the openQKD infrastructure, tests and benchmarks, publication of results. During the project and in consultation with the openQKD resource providers, the testbed will be extended/cloned to use real QKD resources, and the final integration and validation steps will be performed. The results of the integration and benchmarks will be discussed with the openQKD members and finally published.

Deliverables/Milestones: Final report on availability and status of the testbed, technology integration and recommendations; publication of results.

Fig. 1: Project Gantt Chart for PM1-PM4

Main Use cases

Use case1: CNN for Detection of Neurological Diseases from MRI Images

Diseases like Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD) and schizophrenia (SZ) are among the most common neurological disorders (NLD). They are characterized by the disruption of regular operations of brain functions. Due to the high impact these diseases have on the quality of life of patients and their families, early detection of such conditions to slow down if not stop the diseases has become a critical field of research. However, direct visual analysis of brain images is far from efficient due to commonality of phenotypic traits across different diseases. In recent times, high-definition neuroimaging techniques such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography (CT) and positron emission tomography (PET) have been combined to deep learning analysis methods to classify these disorders for early detection.

Although research has been performed on application of many different classes of deep learning architectures³, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Long-Short Term

³ Noor, M., Zenia, N. Z., Kaiser, M. S., Mamun, S. A., & Mahmud, M. (2020). Application of deep learning in detecting neurological disorders from magnetic resonance images: a survey on the detection of Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease and schizophrenia. *Brain informatics*, 7(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40708-020-00112-2>

Memory (LSTM), Deep Neural Network (DNN), and Autoencoder (AE), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based approaches have received most of the attention.

Building, training, and applying such models are, however, complex tasks that require a combination of domain expertise of neurology and computer science. Furthermore, with the increasing size of datasets in both dimensionality and number of samples, the computing requirements often go beyond the resources available to individual institutes. Today we can observe a growing trend toward outsourcing the computing infrastructure, which is making Deep Learning as a Service (DLaaS) an increasingly appealing solution. Cloud platforms can be used to either train models or apply pre-learned models, offloading the researchers' burden setting up and managing scalable local resources.

However, the approach has limitations and raises important questions that need to be resolved. The first and foremost concern is that public cloud platforms or shared computing facilities do not guarantee data privacy. In the typical DLaaS platform, users upload data to the cloud, where models are trained, or input data evaluated with pre-trained models. The results are then sent back to the user. Opportunities for attacks and data breaches can occur at any point in the deployed workflows.

Investigations on how to provide secure and efficient solutions to the problem of processing sensitive data on distributed resources are becoming a critical research area. QUANTUMACY proposes to investigate an approach based on Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) to train and evaluate Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) on encrypted data and to combine this approach with QKD-based encryption for the data, the network or both.

Three sub-use cases are considered:

Sub-Case 1: Evaluation of pre-trained models on FHE-encrypted data (Inference) on aggregated data sets

In this use case, the researcher has a set of pre-trained models and a set of MRI scans to be classified. They want to:

- 1) Upload the models and the FHE-encrypted data to a cloud service or shared computing facility via a QKD link.
- 2) Have the cloud service evaluate the model on the encrypted images.
- 3) Retrieve the classification metadata via a QKD link.
- 4) Decrypt the metadata and classify the original dataset

Sub-Case 2: Evaluation of pre-trained models on FHE-encrypted data (Inference) on distributed data sets (Federated Learning)

In this use case, the researcher has a set of pre-trained models, but the set of MRI scans to be classified are stored in encrypted form in different known repositories. They want to:

- 1) Upload the models and the FHE-encrypted data to a federated learning cloud service via a QKD link.
- 2) Have the cloud service evaluate the model on the encrypted images over the local repositories without transferring the images.
- 3) Retrieve the classification metadata via a QKD link.
- 4) Decrypt the metadata and classify the original dataset

Sub-Case 3: Model training on FHE-encrypted data (Training) on aggregated or distributed datasets

In this use case, the researcher has a set of untrained models and training/test dataset of possibly, but not necessarily labelled MRI scans. They want to:

- 1) Upload the models and the FHE-encrypted data to a cloud service or shared computing facility via a QKD link.
- 2) Have the cloud service train the model of the images either in aggregated or distributed form.
- 3) Retrieve the trained models via a QKD link.
- 4) Repeat the process as necessary to validate/test the models.

Privacy Preserving Data Sharing Platform for Health Risk Assessment

In collaborative medical research, the need for data sharing is quite common, especially when the topic deals with some rare medical cases. Medical data can be shared on condition that it is properly de-identified with the review and approval of Institutional Review Boards.

Data de-identification is, however, not an easy-to-handle issue. It is hard to have a well de-identified and, at the same, a good quality dataset, because de-identification is usually done at the cost of the data quality. Noise insertion, discretizing and categorizing values are some examples of de-identifying data.

A measurement value which is in continuous variable can give a good clue to an attacker who has another database and tries to re-identify some instances from the de-identified data set.

Privacy preserving data sharing platform is submitted with the homomorphically encrypted dataset from the collaborating institutions(hospitals). Because the dataset in the platform is homomorphically encrypted, it is safe from the risk of re-identification and privacy leakage.

Each collaborating institution (hospital) can utilize the whole dataset in the platform in the homomorphically encrypted form. By aggregating the whole homomorphically encrypted values on the platform, they can perform some statistical analysis on each local institution such as Student's t-test, chi-square test, anova test, regression, and so on.

Before performing the statistical analysis, some appropriate keys are required for decrypting the aggregated values on a local institution. They can be safely sent through the QKD channels built between collaborating institutions.

Two separate sub-use cases are considered:

Sub-Case 1: Evaluation of pre-trained models on FHE-encrypted data (Inference) on aggregated data sets

1. The institutions (hospitals) encrypt their data homomorphically before they send the data to the platform

2. Each institution can read and aggregate the whole values in HE form

3. Then, individual users can access the risk assessment services sending encrypted data through the QKD channel and retrieve a score. The statistical analysis includes Student's t-test, ANOVA test, chi-squared test, regression, and so on.

In this use case, the same use cases as in sub-case 1 is managed through a block chain ledger that implements GDPR-compliant policies for consent establishment and retrieval and for auditing access to the aggregated encrypted data.

Infrastructure

The QUANTUMACY infrastructure is planned to be deployed across up to four different sites within the participants and external collaborators administrative boundaries, that is at CERN, Be-ys Research, University of Madrid and SNUBH. The real QKD link will be established between the CERN Dta Centre and the SIG data centre where IDQ hosts its hardware. The main resource site and the first prototype will be based at CERN. The following sections describe the nominal configuration of each site, although the type and amount of resources can change during the lifetime of the project.

Resources

Computing resources are available at all sites, albeit in different configurations and amounts. Computing resources include CPU and GPU and are used to perform the different computing tasks, such as data preprocessing, encryption, model training and inference, simulation, block chain management, etc.

Storage resources are available at CERN and SNUBH to store the raw datasets and any relevant processed data or results.

Datasets stored in the repositories are sourced from relevant public data banks for the purpose of demonstrating the assumptions of the QUANTUMACY project and performing the operations required to set up and validate the proposed proof-of-concept. All data used in the project are public or anonymised data. It is beyond the scope of the project to use real data, although at the end of the project, some considerations of how to implement operations with real personal data will be drawn. More specifically, the following datasets are used:

- 1) RSNA Chest
- 2) RSNA Brain
- 3) Extracted anonymised datasets of typical medical conditions to evaluate the health risk assessment score

A variety of services and tools is expected to be used during the execution of the project for development and execution. However, in particular the following tools will be used for the main functions:

- **EOS:** EOS is a disk-based, low-latency storage service developed at CERN for physics data storage. Today, EOS provides storage for both physics and user use cases. Instances of EOS include EOSUSER, EOSPUBLIC, EOSATLAS,

EOSCMS. The main target area for the service is physics data analysis, which is characterised by many concurrent users, a significant fraction of random data access and a large file-open rate, but it is being assessed for different types of research use cases, such as genomic analysis, or climate and earth observation. For user authentication EOS supports Kerberos (for local access) and X.509 certificates for grid access. More information at <https://information-technology.web.cern.ch/services/eos-service>

- **SWAN:** SWAN (Service for Web based ANalysis) is a platform to perform interactive data analysis in the cloud. It allows to analyse data without the need to install any software using a Jupyter notebook interface as well as shell access directly from standard web browsers. It uses CERNBox as home directory and synchronise the local user storage with the cloud
- **CERNBox:** CERNBox provides cloud data storage to all CERN users and CERN account holders. It's possible to store your data, share it and synchronise it across devices. The data can be accessed from any Web browser or file explorer (using WebDav), and allows you to decide what data you want to share with other individuals or groups of collaborators. Data can be synchronised to different devices (Windows, Mac, Linux, iOS and Android) with dedicated CERNBox applications. CERNBox also integrates with some applications to allow collaborative editing of interactive notebooks for Physics analysis, as well as other products. It also allows creating dedicated projects spaces to be shared across all users of a project.

QKD simulation resources will be installed during the initial phase of the project after the evaluation of the current state-of-the-art is completed. The resources will include a set of endpoints with simulated QKD services based on one or more standard protocols (BB84, E91, BB92, ec.).

Physical QKD links will be set up in agreement with the openQKD resource managers within 6 months of the start of the project. The links to be used for the tests will be negotiated depending on availability,

Software Engineering Tools

The software engineering process is based on a simplified agile methodology with weekly mini-sprints across four different teams (Development of Use Case 1, Development of Use Case 2, QKD simulation and deployment, block chain and user tools). Each teams meets separately at least once a week and a weekly integration meeting takes place to share information on progress and platform integration.

Software development is based on a common source code repository hosted at github (<https://github.com/CERN/Quantumacy>). The repository is kept private during the initial phases of the project, but will be made publicly available under MIT open source license before the end of the project.

Each team uses the software development tools and frameworks necessary for its part of the development, The tools are made available through the SWAN/Jupyter framework whenever possible, otherwise dedicated nodes are available within the CERN openlab resource testbed at CERN with root access for development and tests.

Deployment Architecture

Site 1 (CERN)

CERNBox: a dedicated CERNBox home directory is provided to each project member at <https://cernbox.cern.ch>

EOS: a shared repository with 2TB of space has been created to store all project datasets. The repository is available to all project members. Additionally project members have a dedicated quota per personal development as part of their CERNBox home directory

Four dedicated nodes have been set up for the Quantumacy project to deploy the user web application (data encryption/decryption, workflow submission) and the storage and computing nodes of the aggregated and federated learning pipelines.

Site 2 (Be-ys Research)

It will be provided starting at PM3 based on requirements

Site 3 (SNUBH)

SNUBH provides storage space and local computing space. However, since SNUBH is an external collaborator, no commitment is requested or expected

Site 4 (Madrid)

University of Madrid can facilitate access to QKD links from the local openQKD site. The feasibility will be assessed in during the deployment phase from PM6

Site 5 (Geneva)

SIG (Service Industriel de Geneve) can facilitate access to QKD links from the local openQKD site. The feasibility will be assessed in during the deployment phase from PM6

Technology

CNN-based Image Analysis

Image classification is the process of segmenting images into different categories based on their features. A feature could be the edges in an image, the pixel intensity, the change in pixel values, and many more. The biggest challenge when working with images is the uncertainty of these features.

CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) is a class of deep learning neural networks that can take in an input image, assign importance (learnable weights and biases) to various aspects/objects in the image, and be able to differentiate one from the other. CNN works by extracting features from the images. Popular CNN already exist for object detection and object category classification from images, like Alex Nets, GoogLeNet, and ResNet50. A variety of image data sets are available to test the performance of different types of CNN's. The commonly found benchmark datasets for evaluating the performance of a convolutional neural network are anImageNet dataset, and CIFAR10, CIFAR100, and MNIST image data sets.

Typically, any CNN consists of an input layer (a grayscale image), an output layer (a binary or multi-class set of labels), and a number of hidden layers consisting of convolution layers, ReLU (rectified linear unit) layers, pooling layers, and a fully connected Neural Network for the classification. For the Quantumacy project a simple CNN network will be developed (together with a base regression model for comparison) and adapted to work with the selected encryption scheme with and without quantum keys. Although the intention is to work with a medically relevant use case as presented

Homomorphic Encryption

Homomorphic Encryption is a property of an encryption scheme which permits the evaluation of operations without revealing the operands. While there are many variations of these algorithms, Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) schemes are those permitting a potentially unlimited evaluation of operations. On the other hand, Levelled Homomorphic Encryption schemes employ rescaling for the evaluation of the schemes, permitting only a predefined amount of operation, although at a reduced computational expense.

Modern Homomorphic Encryption schemes are based on variations of the Ring Learning with Errors Problem adapted for different arithmetic types (i.e., boolean, integer and decimal). While classical DL structures are based on floating point arithmetic operations, some SoA approaches have used approximations to discretized and binarized neural networks. For simplicity, we choose in this case floating point schemes, in this case, the only available scheme is CKKS / HEANN in one of its open-source implementations (SEAL, HELib or HEANN). The election of the parameters for such implementations will be done according to the circuits chosen for each task.

Given the immaturity of the DL training with HE, other variants of multiparty HE may be considered in that case.

Quantum Key Distribution

Quantum key distribution (QKD) is a secure communication method which implements a cryptographic protocol involving components of quantum mechanics. It enables two parties to produce a shared random secret key known only to them, which can then be used to encrypt and decrypt messages. An important and unique property of quantum key distribution is the ability of the two communicating users to detect the presence of any third party trying to gain knowledge of the key. This results from a fundamental aspect

of quantum mechanics: the process of measuring a quantum system in general disturbs the system. A third party trying to eavesdrop on the key must in some way measure it, thus introducing detectable anomalies. By using quantum superpositions or quantum entanglement and transmitting information in quantum states, a communication system can be implemented that detects eavesdropping. If the level of eavesdropping is below a certain threshold, a key can be produced that is guaranteed to be secure (i.e., the eavesdropper has no information about it), otherwise no secure key is possible and communication is aborted.

The main drawback of quantum key distribution is that it usually relies on having an authenticated classical channel of communications. In modern cryptography, having an authenticated classical channel means that one has either already exchanged a symmetric key of sufficient length or public keys of sufficient security level. With such information already available, one can achieve authenticated and secure communications without using QKD, such as by using the Galois/Counter Mode of the Advanced Encryption Standard. Thus QKD does the work of a Stream Cipher at many times the cost.

Quantum key distribution is only used to produce and distribute a key, not to transmit any message data. This key can then be used with any chosen encryption algorithm to encrypt (and decrypt) a message, which can then be transmitted over a standard communication channel. The algorithm most commonly associated with QKD is the one-time pad, as it is provably secure when used with a secret, random key.

As QKD is today mainly implemented as point-to-point link involving two endpoints connected by a quantum channel, it is usually implemented as a combination of a QKD link with a link encryptor to form a QKD Link Encryptor, a network-transparent cryptographic system. A QKD link encryptor is a Quantum Cryptography appliance for point-to-point link encryption similar to a Virtual Private Network VPN tunnel. The link encryptor usually uses the keys supplied by QKD as keys for a symmetrical block cipher (for example the Advanced Encryption Standard AES) or steam cipher (One Time Pad for highest security) and can be used for example to encrypt traffic on an Ethernet or Fiber Channel link. The QKD Link encryptor may be used to support communications between two adjacent network nodes employing QKD or it may provide protection for communications end-to-end across a network of nodes as a VPN tunnel.

Since physical QKD links are not commodity and will only be available for a limited time during the lifetime of the project, the initial implementation of the QUANTUMACY platform will be based on simulated links. A survey of the state-of-the-art of QKD protocol and channel simulators will be performed at the beginning of the projects and suitable simulated links will be deployed within and among the projects sites. The following list includes the most relevant tools and resources as of February 2021:

- Qskit - <https://qiskit.org/textbook/ch-algorithms/quantum-key-distribution.html>
- QKDNetSim - <https://www.qkdnetstim.info/>,
 - <https://github.com/QKDNetSim/qkdnetstim-dev>
- QKD Simulator - <https://www.qkdsimulator.com/>
- <https://github.com/cotaylor/qkdsim>

- <https://github.com/ShellRox/Quantum-Key-Distribution>

Block Chain

A blockchain is a type of data structure which is replicated, shared, and synchronized across multiple devices that may operate geographically distant from each other. Data synchronization in a blockchain is achieved by using a consensus mechanism among the parties that hold a copy of the blockchain. In this context, consensus refers to a protocol that ensures that parties agree to a specific state of the system as the valid one.

According to the definition given by the Hyperledger project, a blockchain relies on three essential components:

- A data model that captures the current state of the blockchain.
- A language of transactions that can change the blockchain state.
- A protocol used to build consensus among participants around which transactions will be accepted, and in what order, by the blockchain.

As a data structure a blockchain is an append-only chain of blocks that relies on a peer-to-peer network to perform its management, updates and operations. Roughly speaking, blocks are merely containers for transactions, and they can be linked to an existing chain of blocks allowing it to grow.

Furthermore, a blockchain has two distinctive features which are block timestamps and hash pointers that link the last block of the chain to the previous one in such a way that any modification made on a block compels the regeneration of the following blocks in the chain. Together, timestamps and hash pointers can provide the tamper-proof capability to a blockchain and this, in turn, allows it to achieve a high level of security thanks to the immutability guarantees of its data structure. This immutability feature makes the blockchain suitable for accounting, financial transactions, and asset ownership management and transfer.

Alongside immutability, a very close concept is that of compliance. Since it is possible to create tamper-proof (or immutable) records using a blockchain, even in scenarios where parties may not fully nor partially trust each other, a blockchain can also be suitable for attestation of compliance. For instance, concerning the manipulation of specific data, the certification of compliance can be beneficial.

Hyperledger Fabric

Hyperledger Fabric is an enterprise-grade permissioned blockchain framework backed by the Linux Foundation and IBM among others. As a framework, its modular and versatile design provide unique characteristics to implement different types of customized blockchains according to the purpose, security and performance of a given project. Hyperledger Fabric has three main modules — Membership services, Blockchain services and Chaincode services. Membership services are the place where any new member must be enrolled before joining the network; this is a Certificate Authority (CA), responsible for the user administration, key lifecycle, certificate issuance and maintenance of a node blacklist. Blockchain services have the consensus module and correspond to the actual ledger and the P2P protocol. The chaincode services module contains the “chaincode”, which are Smart Contracts in dockerized

containers. The entire architecture of Fabric is modular, making it easy to plug and play different modules in the system. A separate service "Ordered" (or ordering service) is responsible for transactions order in a block (*i.e.* running the consensus algorithm).

Objectives

Quantumacy will explore the opportunities of integrating the different technologies involved in the data sharing process and QKD with a blockchain network to better support the use cases, providing traceability and auditability features. To that end, Hyperledger Fabric's framework will be used to define an authenticated network of participants.

Another key point to be explored is the integration of the GDPM technology being patented by Be-ys Research to enable more use cases where different parties, that may not know each other fully, can share datasets with the aid of a trusted third party for specific use purposes and while being compliant with existing regulations.

The specific use cases and the architecture of the services to be deployed will be defined after the completion of the first prototypes of the computing services at PM9.

References:

[Online]. Hyperledger Fabric: <https://hyperledger-fabric.readthedocs.io/en/release-1.4/>

[Online]. [D5.1 Blockchain Design Specifications](#). Curex Project: <https://curex-project.eu/content/deliverables>